

Figure 3_supplemental. Description of the activity for the storm producing 13 gigantic jets (Storm 2): Time series of the lightning activity in terms of CG flash rates (blue curve for negative (-CG) and red for positive (+CG) including possible misclassified +IC, respectively) in $(5 \text{ min})^{-1}$, total flash rate (purple curve), peak current for all discharges detected by GLD360 (orange dots), and jets observation (diamonds).